

Supplementary Fig. 1 | Detection of 560-km discontinuity from previous seismic observations^{1,2}. A confident detection of the 560-km discontinuity is indicated by a higher S560/S410 amplitude ratio. Red circles: major mantle plumes; red lines: plate boundaries; thick red lines: subduction zone; triangle: distribution of deep diamonds.

Supplementary Fig. 2 | Composition of garnet in subducted oceanic crust. Yellow circles: garnet from diamond inclusion with HIMU-rich signature³; green circles: garnet inclusions with high Fe³⁺ content from deep mantle^{4,5}; purple circles: pyrolitic garnet⁶⁻⁸; blue circles: garnet in subducted oceanic crust assumed based on MORB composition⁹; orange star: average composition of garnet in subducted oceanic crust⁹; orange lines: the iron content in our two starting glass samples.

Supplementary Fig. 3 | Mössbauer spectra of the two starting materials. a, Glass with $X_{\text{Fe}}=0.19$. **b**, Glass with $X_{\text{Fe}}=0.48$. Both spectra were fitted to two doublets using Gaussian function. Orange: doublet 1, Fe^{3+} ; blue: doublet 2, Fe^{2+} ; green: the overall fit to the data from the sum of subcomponents.

Supplementary Fig. 4 | Representative mapping figures from the system with C-normal and Fe-enriched system at 1600°C.

Supplementary Fig. 5 | The variation of the composition of the garnet in the products compared to the starting materials. a, Normal oceanic crust. b, Iron-enriched oceanic crust. Gray: SiO₂; orange: MgO; blue: Al₂O₃; green: FeO; brown: CaO; lines: initial cation number in the starting materials; open: C-normal system; close: C-enriched system.

Supplementary Fig. 6 | The composition of garnet and carbonate in the products. a, Garnet. b, Carbonate. Light blue circles: garnet in subducted oceanic crust assumed based on MORB composition⁹. Circles: normal oceanic crust; diamonds: Fe-enriched oceanic crust; brown: starting materials; orange: 1600°C; dark blue: 1200°C; shaded area: C-enriched system.

Supplementary Fig. 7 | Velocity impedance contrast of compressional wave at 560-km depth.
a, Oceanic crust with an average initial Ca content of $X_{Ca}=0.38$. **b**, Oceanic crust with a high initial Ca content of $X_{Ca}=0.48$. Contour: compressional-wave impedance contrast.

Supplementary Fig. 8 | Velocity impedance contrast in the Ca-rich oceanic crust at 560-km depth. **a**, I_{PP} of oceanic crust with an average initial Ca content. **b**, I_{SS} of oceanic crust with an average initial Ca content. **c**, I_{PP} of oceanic crust with a high initial Ca content. **d**, I_{SS} of oceanic crust with a high initial Ca content. Contour: impedance contrast; shaded area: I_{SS} determined by seismic studies².

Supplementary Table 1. Chemical Compositions of the Recovered Products at Different Conditions.

Run No.	T (°C)	Fe content (mol%)	CaCO ₃ Content (wt%)	Phase	MgO (wt%)	Al ₂ O ₃ (wt%)	SiO ₂ (wt%)	CaO (wt%)	FeO (wt%)	CO ₂ (wt%)	Total
1k3960	1600	19.1	10	Grt	24.8(10)	12.7(4)	50.3(10)	1.0(3)	10.7(5)		99.5(9)
				Dm	1.3(7)	1.7(3)	47.6(11)	44.9(13)	1.0(3)	96.5(13)	
				Mag	40.8(6)	0.22(7)	1.1(2)	0.87(8)	7.5(7)	50.4(2)	100.8(5)
1k3960	1600	19.1	50	Grt	8.7(5)	21.3(6)	40.8(7)	19.9(11)	9.4(10)		100.0(11)
				Dm	0.09(3)	1.65(10)	45.6(5)	46.2(5)	0.40(5)	93.9(5)	
				Mag	37.3(11)	0.19(1)	1.3(9)	3.0(10)	10.4(6)	49.3(7)	101.5(31)
1k3960	1600	47.8	10	Grt	13.3(5)	15.3(8)	46.2(10)	7.0(5)	18.6(6)		100.4(9)
				Mag	36.3(7)	0.4(3)	1.3(9)	0.8(1)	12.7(8)	49.3(2)	101(1)
				Hem	3.1(3)	1.1(2)	2.3(9)	0.5(2)	87.1(20)	94.2(11)	
1k3960	1600	47.8	50	Grt	5.4(12)	19.6(6)	40.2(5)	16.2(7)	17.6(7)		99.0(9)

				Dm	0.4(3)	2.2(6)	46.9(14)	45.1(11)	1.1(6)		95.7(19)
				Mag	34.5(11)	0.12(5)	0.2(1)	2.3(3)	16.7(14)	47.8(6)	101.7(15)
				Stv	0.08(3)	1.5(2)	96.5(14)	1.0(5)	0.29(8)		99.4(8)
1k3970	1200	19.1	10	Grt	25.3(7)	13.5(3)	49.3(14)	0.5(1)	10.8(4)		99.4(12)
				Mag	40.8(12)	0.3(2)	1.7(10)	1.2(6)	7.2(5)	50.4(4)	101.7(21)
1k3970	1200	19.1	50	Grt	22.5(4)	14.4(4)	51.3(7)	2.2(4)	10.5(2)		100.9(9)
				Dm	4.7(22)	11.8(38)	37.9(26)	32.2(39)	2.5(7)		89.1(34)
				Arg	0.5(3)	0.5(2)	0.4(2)	53.5(8)	0.26(8)	44.4(2)	99.7(3)
1k3970	1200	47.8	10	Grt	14.0(7)	16.5(16)	44.8(26)	4.2(8)	20.2(32)		99.7(7)
				Mag	35.9(30)	1.0(2)	5.9(20)	3.9(14)	9.1(26)		100
				Hem	2.3(2)	1.1(4)	1.1(4)	0.5(3)	86.5(9)		91.6(4)
1k3970	1200	47.8	50	Grt	4.2(7)	19.7(8)	40.2(8)	16.5(9)	18.9(5)		99.4(14)
				Dm	1.3(4)	2.9(20)	46.0(1)	43.0(21)	2.1(9)		95.3(10)

Hem	0.7(3)	2.5(10)	1.9(24)	2.1(21)	81.9(43)		89.1(48)
Arg	0.09(6)	0.1(1)	0.2(3)	55.5(6)	0.63(9)	43.9(1)	100.4(4)

Note: The composition of stishovite, magnesite, or davemaoite in some runs are hard to determine because of the small size, which is not included in this table.

Supplementary Table 2. Modal proportion based on mass balance calculation and BSE images mapping.

Sample No.	Mass balance calculation (wt.%)								BSE (vol.%)					
	Stv	Garnet	Mag	Dm	Hem	Arg	Total	Residual SSQ	Stv	Garnet	Mag	Dm	Hem	Arg
1200- $X_{Fe}=0.19-10\%$ CaCO ₃	0	80.4	10.2	9.4	0	0	100	60.7	0	95	4	1	0	0
1200- $X_{Fe}=0.19-50\%$ CaCO ₃	0.5	15.0	20.2	38.7	0.0	25.6	100.0	15.8	0	88	3	9	0	6.3
1600- $X_{Fe}=0.19-10\%$ CaCO ₃	0.0	80.6	10.6	8.1	0.0	0.0	99.3	68.7	1	86	9	4	0	0
1600- $X_{Fe}=0.19-50\%$ CaCO ₃	0	11.8	38.8	47.1	0	0	97.7	70.3	0	70	13	17	0	0
1200- $X_{Fe}=0.48-10\%$ CaCO ₃	13.2	62.4	20.4	4.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	108.7	0	88	6	4	2	0
1200- $X_{Fe}=0.48-50\%$ CaCO ₃	2.0	11.9	31.2	38.4	0.0	15.9	99.5	21.4	0	59	5	20	2	14
1600- $X_{Fe}=0.48-10\%$ CaCO ₃	11.3	70.4	17.5	0.7	0.0	0.0	100.0	119.7	3	79	8	2	8	0
1600- $X_{Fe}=0.48-50\%$ CaCO ₃	0.0	0.6	42.1	55.7	0.0	0.0	98.3	45.9	2	59	13	25	1	0

Supplementary Table 3. Elasticity data used in modeling

Mineral	Formula	ρ (g/cm ³)	K_{S0} (GPa)	K_{S0}'	$\partial K/\partial T$	G_0	G_0'	$\partial G/\partial T$	α_0 (10 ⁻⁵)	α_1 (10 ⁻⁸)	α_2	γ
Davemaoite ¹⁰	CaSiO ₃	4.233	248(3)	4.2(2)	-0.036(1)	126(1)	1.6(1)	-0.015(1)	2.00	1.90		1.45
Grossular-Andradite ¹¹⁻¹⁷	Ca ₃ Al ₂ Si ₃ O ₁₂ - Ca ₃ Fe ₂ Si ₃ O ₁₂	3.597+0.25*X _{Fe3}	167(2)-12*X _{Fe3}	4.8(1)	-0.0196(1)	107(1)-18*X _{Fe3}	1.3(1)	-0.01(1)	2.84	-	-0.4	1.22
Majorite-Fe Majorite ¹⁸⁻²⁰	Mg ₄ Si ₄ O ₁₂ - Fe ₄ Si ₄ O ₁₂	3.52(1)+0.01*X _{Fe2}	160(3)	4.3(2)	-0.014(2)	86(2)	1.3(2)	-0.008(1)	2.88	0.279	-0.5521	1.2
Pyrope-Almandine ^{11,12,21-28}	Mg ₃ Al ₂ Si ₃ O ₁₂ - Fe ₃ Al ₂ Si ₃ O ₁₂	3.566(3)+0.75*X _{Fe2}	173(2)+ *X _{Fe2}	4.1(2)+0.8*X _{Fe2}	-0.017(2)- 0.003*X _{Fe2}	92(2)+5*X _{Fe2}	1.4(1)	-0.01(1)- 0.001*X _{Fe2}	2.311	0.596	-0.4538	1.2
Khoharite*	Mg ₃ Fe ₂ Si ₃ O ₁₂	3.862(8)	163(3)	4.1(2)	-0.017(2)	76(3)	1.4(1)	-0.01(1)	2.311	0.596	-0.4538	1.2

X_{Fe2}, X_{Fe3}: Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ content in mole%

*Estimated followed the method in a previous study²⁹.

Reference

- 1 Deuss, A. & Woodhouse, J. Seismic observations of splitting of the mid-transition zone discontinuity in Earth's mantle. *Science* **294**, 354-357, doi:10.1126/science.1063524 (2001).
- 2 Tian, D., Lv, M., Wei, S. S., Dorfman, S. M. & Shearer, P. M. Global variations of Earth's 520- and 560-km discontinuities. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* **552**, doi:10.1016/j.epsl.2020.116600 (2020).
- 3 Huang, S. *et al.* HIMU geochemical signature originating from the transition zone. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* **542**, doi:10.1016/j.epsl.2020.116323 (2020).
- 4 Kiseeva, E. S. *et al.* Oxidized iron in garnets from the mantle transition zone. *Nat. Geosci.* **11**, 144-147, doi:10.1038/s41561-017-0055-7 (2018).
- 5 Xu, C. *et al.* Recovery of an oxidized majorite inclusion from Earth's deep asthenosphere. *Sci. Adv.* **3**, e1601589, doi:10.1126/sciadv.1601589 (2017).
- 6 Saikia, A., Frost, D. J. & Rubie, D. C. Splitting of the 520-kilometer seismic discontinuity and chemical heterogeneity in the mantle. *Science* **319**, 1515-1518, doi:10.1126/science.1152818 (2008).
- 7 Sanehira, T. *et al.* Density profiles of pyrolite and MORB compositions across the 660 km seismic discontinuity. *High Pressure Res.* **28**, 335-349, doi:10.1080/08957950802251357 (2008).
- 8 Irifune, T., Sekine, T., Ringwood, A. E. & Hibberson, W. O. The eclogite-garnetite transformation at high pressure and some geophysical implications. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* **77**, 245-256, doi:10.1016/0012-821x(86)90165-2 (1986).
- 9 Stracke, A., Willig, M., Genske, F., Béguelin, P. & Todd, E. (GRO.data, 2022).
- 10 Gréaux, S. *et al.* Sound velocity of CaSiO₃ perovskite suggests the presence of basaltic crust in the Earth's lower mantle. *Nature* **565**, 218-221, doi:10.1038/s41586-018-0816-5 (2019).
- 11 Conrad, P. G., Zha, C. S., Mao, H. K. & Hemley, R. J. The high-pressure, single-crystal elasticity of pyrope, grossular, and andradite. *Am. Mineral.* **84**, 374-383 (1999).
- 12 Wang, Z. & Ji, S. Elasticity of six polycrystalline silicate garnets at pressure up to 3.0

- GPa. *Am. Mineral.* **86**, 1209-1218, doi:10.2138/am-2001-1009 (2001).
- 13 Bass, J. D. Elasticity of grossular and spessartite garnets by brillouin spectroscopy. *J. Geophys. Res.:Solid Earth* **94**, 7621-7628, doi:10.1029/JB094iB06p07621 (1989).
- 14 Gwanmesia, G. D., Wang, L., Heady, A. & Liebermann, R. C. Elasticity and sound velocities of polycrystalline grossular garnet ($\text{Ca}_3\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_3\text{O}_{12}$) at simultaneous high pressures and high temperatures. *Phys. Earth Planet. Inter.* **228**, 80-87, doi:10.1016/j.pepi.2013.09.010 (2014).
- 15 Isaak, D. G., Anderson, O. L. & Oda, H. High-temperature thermal-expansion and elasticity of calcium-rich garnets. *Phys. Chem. Miner.* **19**, 106-120 (1992).
- 16 Kono, Y., Greaux, S., Higo, Y., Ohfuji, H. & Irifune, T. Pressure and temperature dependences of elastic properties of grossular garnet up to 17 GPa and 1650 K. *J. Earth Sci.* **21**, 782-791, doi:10.1007/s12583-010-0112-2 (2010).
- 17 Milani, S. *et al.* Thermo-elastic behavior of grossular garnet at high pressures and temperatures. *Am. Mineral.* **102**, 851-859, doi:10.2138/am-2017-5855 (2017).
- 18 Sinogeikin, S. V. Elasticity of majorite and a majorite-pyrope solid solution to high pressure: Implications for the transition zone. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **29**, doi:10.1029/2001gl013937 (2002).
- 19 Ohtani, E., Kagawa, N. & Fujino, K. Stability of majorite (Mg, Fe) SiO_3 at high-pressures and 1800 °C. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* **102**, 158-166, doi:10.1016/0012-821x(91)90005-3 (1991).
- 20 Sinogeikin, S. V. & Bass, J. D. Elasticity of majorite and a majorite-pyrope solid solution to high pressure: Implications for the transition zone. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **29**, doi:10.1029/2001gl013937 (2002).
- 21 Arimoto, T., Greaux, S., Irifune, T., Zhou, C. Y. & Higo, Y. Sound velocities of $\text{Fe}_3\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_3\text{O}_{12}$ almandine up to 19 GPa and 1700 K. *Phys. Earth Planet. Inter.* **246**, 1-8, doi:10.1016/j.pepi.2015.06.004 (2015).
- 22 Chen, G. L., Miletich, R., Mueller, K. & Spetzler, H. A. Shear and compressional mode measurements with GHz ultrasonic interferometry and velocity-composition systematics for the pyrope-almandine solid solution series. *Phys. Earth Planet. Inter.* **99**, 273-287, doi:10.1016/s0031-9201(96)03205-0 (1997).

- 23 Jiang, F. M., Speziale, S. & Duffy, T. S. Single-crystal elasticity of grossular- and almandine-rich garnets to 11 GPa by Brillouin scattering. *J. Geophys. Res.: Solid Earth* **109**, doi:10.1029/2004jb003081 (2004).
- 24 Sinogeikin, S. V. & Bass, J. D. Single-crystal elasticity of pyrope and MgO to 20 GPa by Brillouin scattering in the diamond cell. *Phys. Earth Planet. Inter.* **120**, 43-62, doi:10.1016/s0031-9201(00)00143-6 (2000).
- 25 Leitner, B. J., Weidner, D. J. & Liebermann, R. C. Elasticity of single-crystal pyrope and implications for garnet solid-solution series. *Phys. Earth Planet. Inter.* **22**, 111-121, doi:10.1016/0031-9201(80)90052-7 (1980).
- 26 Liu, Z. D. *et al.* Elastic wave velocity of polycrystalline $Mj_{80}Py_{20}$ garnet to 21 GPa and 2,000 K. *Phys. Chem. Miner.* **42**, 213-222, doi:10.1007/s00269-014-0712-y (2015).
- 27 O'Neill, B., Bass, J. D., Rossman, G. R., Geiger, C. A. & Langer, K. Elastic properties of pyrope. *Phys. Chem. Miner.* **17**, 617-621 (1991).
- 28 Fei, Y. in *Mineral Physics & Crystallography AGU Reference Shelf* 29-44 (American Geophysical Union, 1995).
- 29 Vasiukov, D. M. *et al.* Sound velocities of skiagite-iron-majorite solid solution to 56 GPa probed by nuclear inelastic scattering. *Phys. Chem. Miner.* **45**, 397-404, doi:10.1007/s00269-017-0928-8 (2018).